

USING DEEP LEARNING FOR IMAGE-BASED CROP DISEASE DETECTION IN ABUJA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Image-based plant leaves diseases detector for five Nigerian crops were developed using deep learning approach. A locally collected dataset of 268 images of diseased and healthy plant leaves collected under controlled conditions were used. A deep convolutional neural network was trained to identify the five crop diseases namely Sorghum anthracnose, Cowpea *Cercospora* leaf spot, Maize phosphorus deficiency, Rice brown leaf spot and Sunflower leaf blight. The trained model achieved a top accuracy of 94.03% i.e. 940 out of 1000 images on a held-out test set, demonstrating the feasibility of this approach. Overall, the approach of training deep learning models on increasingly large and publicly available image datasets presents a clear path toward smartphone-assisted crop disease detection and management in Nigeria and on a massive global scale.

Keywords: Computer vision, Crop diseases, Deep learning, Machine learning

INTRODUCTION

The potential to produce enough food to suit the needs of more than 7 billion people has been provided by modern technologies. However, a number of factors continue to pose a threat to food security, including plant diseases (Hughes, D. P., and Salathé, M. (2015), pollinator decline (Report of the Plenary of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity Ecosystem and Services on the work of its Fourth Session, 2016), climate change (Tai et al., 2014) and others. Food security is seriously threatened by crop diseases, but because the essential infrastructure is lacking in many areas of sub-Saharan Africa, it is still difficult to identify them quickly.

Smartphone-aided disease diagnosis has been made possible by the rise in smartphone usage and current developments in computer vision made possible by deep learning. Plant diseases are a

threat to global food security, but they can also have devastating effects on smallholder farmers whose livelihoods depend on producing healthy crops. More than 80% of agricultural production in the developing countries is produced by smallholder farmers (UNEP, 2013), and reports of yield losses of more than 50% due to pests and diseases are frequent (Harvey et al., 2014). Smallholder farmers are a population that is particularly sensitive to disruptions in the food supply caused by pathogens because the majority of hungry people (50%) live in these homes (FAO, 2017).

Many initiatives have been created to stop crop loss from diseases. In the past ten years, integrated pest management (IPM) strategies have progressively augmented historical methods for the extensive administration of pesticides (Braga *et al.*, 2020). Whatever the method, the first step in effective plant disease management is accurate disease identification when it first manifests.

Historically, institutions like local plant clinics or agricultural extension agencies have assisted disease identification. More recently, these initiatives have also been helped by making disease diagnosis information available online, utilizing the expanding global internet resources. Even more recently, mobile phone-based tools have expanded quickly, capitalizing on the historically unprecedented global adoption of mobile phone technology (The Global Information Technology Report, 2015).

Due to their powerful computational capabilities, sharp screens, and comprehensive built-in accessory sets, such as high-definition cameras, smartphones in particular provide a particularly new method of aiding in the diagnosis of diseases. Approximately 63% of the world's population, or 5 billion people, were internet users as of April 2022 (WDP, 2022). It is now possible to diagnose diseases using automatic picture identification on a scale never before possible thanks to the expanded smartphone market, HD cameras, and high-performance processors in mobile devices. Using locally acquired 268 photos of five crop species with five diseases, we show in this study that it is technically feasible to use a deep learning approach (or healthy). Figure 1 displays a sample of each crop-disease pair.

In the past few years, especially, developments in computer vision and object identification have been enormous. The PASCAL VOC Challenge (Everingham *et al.*, 2010) and, more recently, the Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) (Russakovsky *et al.*, 2015) based on the ImageNet dataset (Deng *et al.*, 2009; Russakovsky *et al.*, 2015) have been widely used as benchmarks for a variety of visualization-related issues in computer vision, including object classification. (Krizhevsky *et al.*, 2012). Deep convolutional neural network advancements during the subsequent three years reduced the error rate to 3.57%. (Krizhevsky *et al.*, 2012; Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014; Zeiler and Fergus, 2014; He *et al.*, 2015; Szegedy *et al.*, 2015). The trained models can swiftly classify photos, which makes them acceptable for consumer applications on smartphones even though training big neural networks can take a long time.

Recently, deep neural networks have been successfully used in a wide range of applications. An image of a damaged plant as an input and a crop disease pair as an output are mapped using neural

networks. The mathematical nodes in a neural network receive numerical inputs from the incoming edges and output numerical results as the outgoing edges. A sequence of stacked layers of nodes in deep neural networks simply map the input layer to the output layer. The difficult part of building a deep network is making sure that the network's structure, functions (nodes), and edge weights accurately map the input to the output.

Deep neural networks are trained by adjusting the network parameters so that the mapping gets better during the course of training. This computationally difficult technique has recently seen significant improvements because to a number of conceptual and engineering advancements (LeCun *et al.*, 2015; Schmidhuber, 2015). In this study, we describe how a convolutional neural network technique was used to classify 5 diseases in five crop species using 268 photo images.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Dataset Description

Two hundred and sixty-eight (268) images of diseased crop leaves were collected on crop farms of Teaching and Research Farms of University of Abuja, Abuja Nigeria and were analysed and categorized. The collected crop leaf samples were assigned five class labels. From the image of the plant leaf, the crop diseases were predicted. The image of crop disease sample from the dataset is as shown in Fig.1. In all the approaches used and described in this study, each of the images were resized to 224×224 pixels, and both the model optimization and predictions on the downscaled images were performed.

In this study, the whole dataset was used for training and validation. The training was performed on two versions of the locally-sourced dataset (colour and grayscale). The study was designed to understand if the Neural Network (NN) actually learns the "notion" of plant diseases and not just the inherent biases in the dataset. When designing the experiments, it was noted that the neural networks might only learn to pick up the inherent biases associated with the lighting conditions, the method and apparatus of collection of the data, we therefore experimented with the gray-scaled version of the same dataset to test the model's adaptability in the absence of color information, and its ability to learn higher level structural patterns typical to particular crops and diseases.

FIGURE 1: Example of leaf images from dataset. (1) Anthracnose, (2) Cercospora leaf spot, (3) Phosphorus deficiency, (4) Rice brown leaf spot, (5) Sunflower leaf blight.

Fig.1: Samples of Leaf images from dataset i. Sorghum anthracnose, ii. Cowpea Cercospora leaf spot, iii. Maize phosphorus deficiency, iv. Rice brown leaf spot v. Sunflower leaf blight

Measurement of Performance

To get a sense of how the approaches (models) perform or generalize on new unseen data, and also to keep a track of if any of these models were overfitting. The experiments were run at a ratio of 80 - 20 train-test set splits (80% of the whole dataset used for training, and 20% for testing). It must be noted that in many cases, the collected dataset has multiple images of the same leaf (taken from different orientations). During all these test-train splits, it was ascertained that all the images of the same leaf go either in the training set or the testing set.

Approach

The applicability of deep convolutional neural networks for the crop disease detection problem described above were evaluated. The type of algorithm i.e., architecture used were LeNet -5 (LeCun *et al.*, 1998) and EfficientNetB0 (ICML 2019). The LeNet-5 architecture variants are a set of stacked convolution layers followed by one or more fully connected layers. The convolution layers optionally may have a normalization layer and a pooling layer right after them, and all the layers in the network usually have ReLu non-linear activation units associated with them. The performance of the architectures on the dataset were analysed by training the model from scratch in one case, then by using transfer learning (trained on the ImageNet dataset). When training the model, the learning of any of the layers were not limited, as is sometimes done for transfer learning. In other words, the key difference between these two learning approaches (transfer vs. training from

scratch) is in the initial state of weights of a few layers, which lets the transfer learning approach exploit the large amount of visual knowledge already learned by the pre-trained EfficientNetB0 model extracted from ImageNet.

In this study, the following experimental configurations were used:

- I. Choice of deep learning architecture:
 - LeNet
 - EfficientNetB0
- II. Choice of training mechanism:
 - Training from Scratch
 - Transfer Learning
- III. Choice of dataset type:
 - Colour
 - Grayscale
- IV. Choice of training-testing set distribution:
 - Train: 80%, Test: 20%

Each experiment runs for a total of 30 epochs, where one epoch is defined as the number of training iterations in which the particular neural network has completed a full pass of the whole training set. The choice of number of epochs was based on observation in the experiments where the learning always converged well (at 30).

The following hyper-parameters in all of the experiments were used:

- Solver type: Adam,
- Loss: categorical cross-entropy
- Base learning rate: 0.005,
- Gamma: 0.1,
- Batch size: 128

All the above experiments were conducted using

Tensorflow (Jia *et al.*, 2014), which is a fast, open-source framework for deep learning. The training was carried out on Google Colab with GPU clutters for faster training.

RESULTS

At the onset, it was noted that on a dataset with 5 class labels, random guessing will only achieve an

overall accuracy of 3.13% on average. Across all our experimental configurations, which included two visual representations of the image data (Figure 2), the overall accuracy we obtained on the dataset varied from 41% to 94% hence showing strong promise of the deep learning approach for similar prediction problems.

FIGURE 2: Sample images from dataset used in various experiments (A) Colour (B) Grayscale.

All the experimental configurations run for a total of 30 epochs each, and they almost consistently converge after the first step down in the learning rate. With training and validation on 80:20 ratio, the model achieved a reasonable accuracy. As expected, the overall performance of the model does degrade if we keep increasing the test set to train set ratio.

The two versions of the dataset (colour and grayscale) showed a characteristic variation in performance across all the experiments when the rest of the experimental configuration were kept

constant. As expected, the performance did decrease when compared to the experiments on the colored version of the dataset. Thus, the models performed best in case of the coloured version of the dataset (**Fig. 4**).

From Fig. 3, the result of loss and accuracy through the training period of 30 epochs across experiments for colour and grayscale images are shown. From the graph of the coloured and grayscale images, it was indicated that accuracies for training and validation increases while the losses decreases. This is an expected and normal trend.

Figure 3: Loss and accuracy through the training period of 30 epochs across experiments for colour and grayscale images.

The models from the experiments were then tested on a held-out sample of coloured and grayscale images and accuracy range between 41.02%-94.03% i.e., the model was correct 94 out of 100, as shown in Fig. 4

Fig. 4: Results gotten from test samples

DISCUSSION

Convolutional neural networks have significantly improved in the past few years at classifying images and recognizing objects. He *et al.* (2015); Zeiler and Fergus (2014); Simonyan and Zisserman (2014); Szegedy *et al.* (2015); Traditionally, learning algorithms have been utilized in feature spaces created by hand-engineering features like SIFT (Daniel *et al.*, 2022; Verdonck *et al.*, 2021; Sarker 2021), for image classification tasks. Thus, the effectiveness of these techniques was strongly influenced by the underlying preset features. The process of feature engineering itself is difficult and complex, and it must be redone whenever the situation at hand or the related dataset significantly alters. This issue arises in all conventional attempts to detect plant diseases using computer vision since they mainly rely on manually built features, picture augmentation techniques, and a variety of other intricate and time-consuming methodologies. Additionally, conventional methods for disease categorization through machine learning typically concentrate on a restricted number of classes, typically within a single crop. Examples include the feature extraction and classification pipeline used with thermal and stereo images to distinguish between tomato powdery mildew and healthy tomato leaves (Raza *et al.*, 2015), the use of RGB

images to detect apple scab (Chéné *et al.*, 2012), and the detection of powdery mildew in uncontrolled environments. *Citrus huanglongbing* is detected via fluorescence imaging spectroscopy (Wetterich *et al.*, 2012) aircraft-based sensors and near-infrared spectral patterns have been used to detect *C. huanglongbing* (Sankaran *et al.*, 2011). (Garcia-Ruiz *et al.*, 2013), the identification of tomato yellow leaf curl virus by means of a series of conventional feature extraction procedures, followed by classification using a support vector machines pipeline. The work in this field is thoroughly covered in a relatively recent study on the application of machine learning to plant phenotyping (Singh *et al.*, 2015). Although neural networks have been used in the past to classify and detect plant diseases in *Phalaenopsis* seedlings, such as bacterial soft rot, bacterial brown spot, and *Phytophthora* black rot (Gangadharan *et al.*, 2020), the method required that the images be represented using a carefully chosen list of texture features before the neural network could classify them.

Our strategy is based on recent research by Krizhevsky *et al.* (2012), which demonstrated for the first time that end-to-end supervised training using a deep convolutional neural network architecture is a realistic option even for image

classification problems with a very large number of classes, outperforming conventional methods using hand-engineered features in standard benchmarks. They are a very attractive option for a practical and scalable method to the computational inference of plant diseases due to the absence of the labor-intensive phase of feature engineering and the generalizability of the solution.

In order to diagnose crop species as well as the presence and identification of diseases on previously unseen photos, we trained a model on photographs of plant leaves using the deep convolutional neural network architecture. This objective has been accomplished as evidenced by the top accuracy of 94.03% within the dataset of 268 photos encompassing 5 classes of 5 crop species and 5 diseases (or absence thereof). Thus, the model properly categorizes crop and diseases from 5 possible classes in 94 out of 100 photos without the use of feature engineering. It is significant to note that, despite the model training taking a long time (between a few minutes and hours on Google Colab), the classification process itself is quick (taking less than a second on a CPU), and can therefore be readily implemented on a smartphone. This shows a clear path toward widespread global smartphone-assisted crop disease diagnosis. However, there are still a lot of issues that need to be resolved in subsequent work. The model's accuracy is slightly worse when tested on a batch of photographs obtained under settings different from those used for training. It's vital to notice that this accuracy is significantly greater than the one based on a randomly chosen sample of 5 classes (2.6%), but the accuracy can still be increased by using a more varied set of training data. Our current findings suggest that adding more (and more variable) data alone will be sufficient to significantly improve the accuracy, hence efforts are being made to acquire this additional data.

The second drawback is that we are now limited to classifying single leaves that are facing up on a uniform background. Although these situations are simple, a real-world program should be able to categorize pictures of a disease as it manifests itself on the plant. In fact, a lot of diseases do not affect just the upper side of the leaves, or even the upper side of the plant at all. Therefore, new image collection initiatives should make an attempt to

acquire images from a variety of angles, ideally in surroundings that are as realistic as possible. However, since growers are supposed to know which crops they are planting, employing 5 groups that include both crop species and disease status has made the issue more difficult than is ultimately necessary. Limiting the classification problem to the disease status won't have a discernible impact given the extremely high accuracy of the locally gathered dataset. On real-world datasets, we can observe appreciable accuracy increases. The effectiveness of our models was assessed by selecting the appropriate crop-disease match among five different classes. The top model's accuracy score was 94.03% overall, demonstrating the technical validity of our technique. Overall, this technique is fairly effective with a variety of crop species and diseases, and it is anticipated to get much better with more training data.

It's important to note that the method described here is meant to complement current disease diagnosis methods rather than to completely replace them. Diagnostics based solely on visual symptoms are inherently unreliable, and it is frequently difficult to make an early-stage diagnosis through visual inspection alone. Nevertheless, considering the growing smartphone prevalence in the world, with about a billion of them in Africa (GSMA Intelligence, 2016)- We do think that the strategy is a workable addition to assist prevent yield loss. Additionally, in the future, image data from a smartphone might be enhanced with location and time data to further increase accuracy. Not to mention, it would be wise to keep in mind the incredible rate at which mobile technology has advanced recently and will do so in the future. We believe it is possible that very accurate diagnostics via a smartphone are only a matter of time given the constantly growing number and quality of sensors on mobile devices.

CONCLUSION

A clear road for smartphone-assisted crop disease identification and management in Nigeria is provided by the method of training deep learning models on progressively larger and publicly accessible image datasets. Our model's accuracy should be improved in subsequent training to almost 100%. Each of Nigeria's agro-ecological zones should develop local data banks for crop and weed diseases to facilitate collaboration with the

worldwide PlantVillage engaged in the collecting of plant data.

Author contributions

Anjorin, T.S. and Ape A.O., conceived the study, collected images and wrote the paper. Onyedikachi, B.O. carried out the image curation and implemented the algorithm described.

Supplementary resources

The data and the code used in this paper are available at the following locations:

Data: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1QfrTB44EIHRzmoReBXVQr7uzF7yHeY4u?usp=sharingCode:https://github.com/benjaminogbonna/plant_disease_identification

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